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EFFECTIVE METHODS USED IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO
FOREIGN STUDENTS

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Annotation: *In this article, successful information from each of the modern methods of foreign language teaching, independent education technologies is analyzed. Allows students to adjust any technology according to the structure, functions, content, goals and objectives of teaching in a specific group of students.*

Key words: *Independent educational technology, communication method, essay, essay reflection, discussion, dialogue, pedagogical system.*

Introduction: Language is the most important means of communication, without which the existence and development of human society is impossible. Today, changes in social relations and means of communication (use of new information technologies) require increasing the communicative competence of students, improving their philological preparation, exchanging ideas in various situations during interaction with them. other communication participants, at the same time, the correct use of the system of language and speech norms and the selection of communicative behavior adequate to the actual communication situation. In other words, the main goal of a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, that is, the ability to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language with native speakers. The educational aspect is an integral part of the educational process, therefore, all educational technologies ensure the education of the necessary qualities of a mature person in students.[1]

Materials and methods: Modern educational technologies used to form the student's communicative competence in a foreign language are the most effective for creating an educational environment that ensures the personal interaction of all participants of the educational process. It is clear that no matter how perfect the use of any teaching technology is, it cannot create the most effective conditions for revealing and developing the abilities of students and creative research of the teacher. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with the lack of positive motivation to learn a foreign language in some students. Positive motivation is not enough, and sometimes there is none, because when learning a foreign language, they face great difficulties and do not master the material due to their psychological characteristics. The main goal of the independent education method is to give students the opportunity to learn independently in the process of solving practical problems or problems that require the integration of knowledge in different fields of science. If we talk about this

method as a pedagogical technology, then this technology implies a complex of research, research, problem-solving methods of a creative nature. Internally, the role of project developer, coordinator, expert, consultant is defined for the teacher.

Results: This technology develops students' creativity, imagination and interests. Creative and intellectual potential of students is revealed during the preparation of independent tasks. The project method teaches research, teamwork, discussion, and problem solving. Life in modern society requires students to develop important cognitive skills such as developing their own thoughts, understanding experience, building a chain of evidence, and expressing their thoughts clearly and convincingly. The technique of developing independent thinking involves asking students questions and understanding the problem to be solved. Critical thinking has an individual independent character, everyone creates their own ideas, forms their own assessments and beliefs independently of others, finds a solution to the problem and supports it with reasonable, reasonable and reliable evidence.[2]

Independent thinking is social because every thought is tested and shared with others. The student's active life position is manifested, especially when comparing previously existing knowledge and concepts with newly acquired knowledge. There are various forms of work that ensure the development of independent thinking of students: essay, essay-reflection, discussion, dialogue, role-playing, etc. In order to develop intercultural communication skills, it is important to give students a thorough knowledge of the culture, customs and traditions of the English-speaking country, so that students can have an objective view and consciously choose their own communication style. They get modeling situations of communication between cultures in English classes allows students to compare the lifestyle characteristics of people in our country and in the countries of the studied language, helps them better understand the culture of our country and develops the ability to express it through English. Such an approach is possible only when using real teaching tools. To find that information and communication technologies are increasingly used in the organization of the educational process, to allow effective consideration of all possible aspects (from linguistics to cultural studies), to improve the speech activity of a foreign language. Their use improves students' linguistic and intercultural competencies helps to improve, to form a culture of communication in the electronic environment, to increase information culture in general, as well as to develop computer skills: search, processing, transfer, systematization. presentation of data and results of research activities by students.[3]

Interactive exercises and tasks performed by students form the basis of interactive approaches. The main difference between independent exercises and ordinary exercises is that they are aimed not only at strengthening the learned material, but also at learning new ones.

Conclusion: New independent education is learning and strengthening the material (interactive lectures, working with visual aids, video and audio materials, "the student as a teacher", "everyone teaches everyone". Complex and controversial under the discussion of issues and problems, creative tasks we understand such educational tasks that require students not to simply repeat information, but creativity, because the tasks contain a more or less element of uncertainty and, as a rule, to several approaches The creative task is the basis of any interactive. Creative task (especially practical and close to the student's life) gives meaning to the study. The uncertainty of the answer and your own "correct" solution. The ability to find based on your personal experience and the experience of your colleague, friend allows you to create a basis for cooperation, joint education, communication of all participants all types and more. Make sure students have the necessary knowledge and skills to complete the group assignment. The lack of knowledge will soon make itself felt. Students do not try to complete the task. You should try to make your instructions as specific as possible. It is unlikely that the group will be able to grasp more than one or two, even very specific, instructions at a time, so the instructions should be written on the board or cards. Give the group enough time to complete the task. When it comes to the practical application of technologies, it is not necessary to use one technology at all. The best way was to combine several educational technologies, combining their best aspects. As we are engaged in the integration of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to form a student's independent education, it is necessary to carefully study the innovative ideas of modern Russian and foreign teachers for several years. It is concluded that this pedagogical system helps to reveal the subjective experience of the student, to form educational work methods that are personally important for him, to educate moral ideals, to develop critical thinking, adequate assessment and self-management.

REFERENCES:

1. Karima Saydanovna Rakhmanberdiyeva. Students in English classes issues of effective speech development.
<https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/180>
2. E.S. Steel. New pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages. Foreign languages at school - 2002 #1. P.22-27.
3. Abdullaeva Marhabo Rakhmonkulovna. (2021). About the process of translation from English to Uzbek and its essence. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION, 2(2), 297-306. Retrieved from <https://summusjournals.uz/index.php/ijdiie/article/view/641>

4. Nasriddinova M.N. Regarding some issues of re-creating ellipsis in translation in fiction. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* Volume 1 | Issue 3, ISSN 2181-1784 Scientific Journal I.F, SJIF 2021: 5.423 pp: 609-614

5. Mukhlisa Nizometdinovna Nasretdinova, & Yuldiz Uktamovna Ishmatova. (2021). EXPRESSION OF THE ELLIPSE PHENOMENON IN TRANSLATIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(10), 11–13. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/87KJS>